

Supplementary Information for:

**A slicing mechanism facilitates host entry by *Phytophthora*
pathogens**

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List of Supplementary Videos

- All videos available on website of original publication
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- *SupplementaryVideo1.avi*
Three-dimensional reconstruction of *P. infestans* invasion into a potato stem: several fluorescent pathogens (*P. infestans* – 14:3 GFP, in green) invade the stem of an etiolated potato cultivar (Bintje), with plant plastids shown in pink, at distinct oblique angles. Scale: the 3D volume has a size of 130 μm (length) x 60 μm (width) x 50 μm (height). Stem surface is located at approximately 35 μm from the base of the volume.
- *SupplementaryVideo2.avi*
Side view of *P. infestans* invasion into an elastomer substrate: Time-series of maximum intensity projections in the XZ-plane showing the invasion of *P. infestans* – 14:3 GFP (green) into a fluorescent elastomer substrate (red).
- *SupplementaryVideo3.avi*
Top view of *P. infestans* invasion into a fracture-reporting substrate: Time-series of maximum intensity projections of *P. infestans* – 14:3 GFP (green) invasion in a fracture-reporting elastomer surface, which is covalently modified to carry the molecular mechanosensor spiropyran (magenta). This movie reveals the initial stage of surface fracture nucleation.
- *SupplementaryVideo4.avi*
Surface deformation maps for *P. infestans* - 14:3 GFP invasion: Right panel: Time-series of reconstructed surface deformation maps for *P. infestans* – 14:3 GFP invasion into a fluorescent elastomer substrate. Color bar indicates surface deformation height in micrometers. Left panel: corresponding GFP channel.
- *SupplementaryVideo5.avi*
Surface deformation maps for *P. palmivora* - wt invasion: Right panel: Time-series of reconstructed surface deformation maps for *P. palmivora* – wt invasion into a fluorescent elastomer substrate. Color bar indicates surface deformation height in micrometers.
- *SupplementaryVideo6.avi*
Surface deformation maps for *P. infestans* - wt invasion: Right panel: Time-series of reconstructed surface deformation maps for *P. infestans* – wt invasion into a fluorescent elastomer substrate. Color bar indicates surface deformation height in micrometers. Left panel: corresponding brightfield channel (black box indicates corresponding area for surface deformation analysis).
- *SupplementaryVideo7.avi*
Surface deformation maps for *P. capsici* - wt invasion: right panel: Time-series of reconstructed surface deformation maps for *P. capsici* – wt invasion into a fluorescent elastomer substrate. Color bar indicates surface deformation height in micrometers.
- *SupplementaryVideo8.avi*
Fitting of surface deformation profiles with model: Time-series of surface deformation profiles (symbols) and fits to the mathematical model (lines) for *P. infestans* – 14:3 GFP invasion into a fluorescent elastomer substrate.

Oomycete strains and growth conditions

P. infestans transformant expressing cytosolic GFP (*P. infestans* 14:3 GFP) [1] was grown on a Rye, Sucrose (2%), Agar (1.5 % technical agar) culture media plate containing 20 µg/mL Vancomycin, 100 µg/mL Ampicillin, 10 µg/mL Amphotericin A and 5 µg/mL Geneticin (RSA-VAAG) in the dark and wrapped in plastic tape. Inoculated plates were incubated by transferring an ≈ 5x5 mm square piece of material from an older plate upside-down onto a fresh RSA-VAAG plate, leaving it for 10-14 days at 20°C to grow before inducing zoospore release. After 10-14 days, zoospore release was achieved by flooding with 10 mL of 4°C sterilized water and then left in a walk-in refrigerator at 4°C for 3 hours. Samples were removed from the fridge, brought to room temperature and gyrated slowly to release the zoospores. All samples were encysted, and 5x/10x diluted with sterilised milli-Q or tap water for experimental use. *P. infestans*-88069 (*wt*) [2] was grown in the same way, but on RSA-VAA medium without Geneticin since this is the transformant selection marker.

P. palmivora-Pp6390 (*wt*) [3] was grown on a (20%)V8-VAA medium (10% V8 juice, 1 g/l CaCO₃, 1.5% technical agar) with 20 µg/mL Vancomycin, 100 µg/mL Ampicillin and 10 µg/mL Amphotericin A. *P. palmivora* was incubated at 25 °C and in continuous high light conditions. Surgical tape was used to close off the petridishes (with nocken), while an excess of evaporated water aggregated inside of the dishes onto the mycelium could pre-empt zoospore release. It was incubated under culture conditions 4-5 days before inducing zoospore release. *P. palmivora* was immersed with 10 ml of sterilised room temperature tap water and left for 30 minutes at room temperature. The plate was slowly gyrated after 30 minutes to resuspend zoospores, encysted and 5x diluted using sterilised tap water.

P. capsici - BYA5 (*wt*) [4] was grown on a (10%)V8 medium (10% V8 juice, 1 g/l CaCO₃, 1.5% technical agar). It was incubated at 25 °C, with a 4 day dark, 4 day light regime to induce sporangium formation. Zoospore release was initiated by flooding the sample with 10 ml sterilised tap water, spending 30 minutes in cold temperatures (4°C) followed by 30 minutes at room temperature.

After releasing, zoospores were encysted using manual shaking for 1 minute (foam forms on top of the solution) directly sporulation. The resulting cyst concentration in the stock suspension was adjusted using 5x/10x dilution to approximately 10⁵ cysts/ml.

Table S5.1. Summary of growth conditions of all used *Phytophthora* species and strains.

Species - strain	Medium	Incubation temperature (°)	Incubation time (days)	Sporulation induction (hr)
<i>P. infestans</i> - 14:3 GFP	RSA-VAAG5	21	10	3
<i>P. infestans</i> - 88069 (<i>wt</i>)	RSA-VAA	21	10	3
<i>P. palmivora</i> - Pp6390 (<i>wt</i>)	(10%)V8-VAA	25	3-4	0.5
<i>P. capsici</i> - BYA5 (<i>wt</i>)	(10%)V8	25	8 (4 dark, 4 light)	1 (.5h 4C, .5h RT)

Artificial Substrates

Preparation

Elastomer surfaces are prepared from a commercial 2-component polydimethyl siloxane rubber (Sylgard 184, Dow Corning) in the following ratios of crosslinker/base: 1/30, 1/10 and 1/5, to obtain different stiffnesses. The two components are accurately weighed on an analytical balance to deviate $< 2\%$ in mass. Before mixing, additives (e.g. Pyrromethene 650 dye for surface deformation profiling, or spiropyran for fracture sensing) are added as stock solutions in toluene. This mixture is thoroughly mixed by vortexing for 3 to 4 minutes. Bubbles and dust are removed from the liquid but viscous mixture by centrifugation at 1000g for 10 minutes.

Glass slides are cleaned prior to spincoating of elastomer precursor mixture. Slides are cleaned by sequential rinsing with isopropyl-alcohol (IPA), Milli-Q deionized water and IPA while being dried using a nitrogen stream between rinsing steps. The slides are dried further by heating to $60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 5 minutes to ensure complete solvent removal after the rinsing steps.

To ensure good adherence of the PDMS rubber to the glass subsurface, slides are pre-treated using an O_2/N_2 plasma for 1 minute just prior to spincoating. After mounting the slide on the spincoater chuck, $150\text{ }\mu\text{l}$ of liquid precursor is placed on the slide. Layers are then prepared by a two-step spincoating procedure: 30 s at 500 rpm to wet the substrate, followed by 2 minutes at 2000 rpm to make a uniform layer of $\approx 33\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ thickness, as determined by confocal microscopy.

Samples are transferred back to a bespoke 3D printed holder, to minimize dust accumulation, and placed inside a vacuum chamber for at least 30 minutes to remove air bubbles. Samples are then placed in a $50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ oven overnight to cure the elastomer. Sensors containing the dye Pyrromethene 650, used in surface deformation profiling, show gradual degradation over several weeks due to dye oxidation and aggregation. These substrates are prepared fresh before each experiment. We (partially) compensate for the loss of crosslink density due to the incorporation of divinyl-spiropyran into the PDMS by increasing the crosslinker content by 50%.

Mechanical characterisation

Since the effective elastic modulus of the substrates is not only a function of the bulk modulus of the material, but is influenced by the presence of a rigid sub-surface due to their limited thickness of approximately 30 micrometers, we measure the Young's modulus of these surfaces in-house. Young's moduli are determined by indentation measurements on a home-built indenter set-up, described in detail in [5].

Briefly, the surfaces are indented using a 0.5 mm diameter spherical steel indenter at a fixed indentation rate of 0.5 mm/s. Resulting force-indentation curves are fitted using a Herzian contact model [6], assuming incompressible substrates with a Poisson's ratio $\nu = \frac{1}{2}$. This model was found to describe the experimental data well and enabled determination of the effective Young's modulus E ; one example of a force-indentation curve and Herzian fits for each substrate are shown in Figure S1. For each sample type, $N = 9$ independent measurements were performed to determine the average value and standard deviation of E ; these results are summarised in Table 2.

Figure S5.1. Results from indentation experiments to characterise the effective Young's modulus of the elastomer substrates; experimental data (black symbols) and fits to a Herzian contact model (red lines).

Crosslinker/Base	Additives	mean E (MPa)	\pm (MPa)
1/30	none or PM650	0.58	0.11
1/10	none or PM650	1.49	0.29
1/5	none or PM650	1.84	0.22
1/20	divinyl spiropyran	0.10	0.0003

Table S5.2. Results of indentation measurements; PM650 = Pyrromethene 650.

Imaging procedure

Confocal microscopy data was acquired on a Nikon Eclipse Ti2 Confocal Laser Scanning Microscope (CLSM) with a 60x oil immersion objective. The scan area was 512x512 pixels with a pixel size of 0.41 $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$, translating into a scan area of 211x211 μm , and a frame acquisition rate of 1/second. For three-dimensional image stacks, a 21 μm deep stack was recorded with a 0.5 micron step size in the axial (z) direction. The acquisition time for a single z-stack is approximately 60 seconds, and these were acquired at 1 stacks per 2 minutes for an effective dark time of 50%. Multiple lasers lines were used to image the various fluorescent components in the PDMS layer and/or oomycetes. GFP expressed in *P. infestans* was excited at 488nm, spiropyran at 640nm and Pyrromethene-650 at 561 nm. Substrates were placed in a

bespoke 3D printed sample chamber (design available as .stl file on request from the authors) to avoid evaporation of medium during imaging experiments. Glass slides containing elastomer substrates were then inoculated with 0.1 ml of a 5x or 10x diluted cyst stock suspension. Another 0.1 ml of the cyst stock was deposited in each of the four corners of upper area the sample chamber to prevent evaporation; the chamber was then sealed with a cell culture dish cover to ensure high humidity conditions over at least an 8 hour period.

For static data collection (e.g. for determining invasion angles), inoculated surfaces were left for 1.5h in a thermostated environment at 20°C prior to imaging. Dynamic data was collected almost immediately after inoculation with a stack-rate of 0.5 stacks/minute. In all experiments, laser powers were minimized as much as possible to prevent dye degradation and light-induced stress to the organisms. Post-experiment, a 3x3 tiling was performed centered around the observed field of view to visually check if germination rates/invasion rates were effected by light exposure. At the used light conditions and dye concentrations no visibly detrimental effect was observed.

Invasion angle measurements

To quantify the invasion angle of many invading microbes, we have developed an automated image analysis routine; code is available per request to the corresponding author. The input data is either a single .tif file that contains three-dimensional image data (xyz), usually from a tiled measurement to increase the number of invasion events per data set. For cytosolic GFP transformants the data is read as is; for wt-species which are not autofluorescent, we stain the PDMS substrate using Pyrromethene 650 and invert the images prior to analysis.

First, we select RoIs that contain a single organism; for each z slice, the image is cropped using the coordinates of the RoI, then filtered using a gaussian filter with a 2-D smoothing kernel with a standard deviation of 0.1, and finally binarized using a threshold that is 30% of the maximum intensity found in the image. The resulting optical sections through the germ tube appear as ellipsoidal shapes. These are recognised using the 'regionprops' function in MatLab, which identifies their centroid coordinate in the xy-plane for each z-slice. For each z slice, the coordinates of the center are compared to the coordinates of the center in the z slice directly above it; the distances are computed using Pythagoras theorem. From these distances, we can also compute, using geometry, the angle between the tube and the flat substrate. To determine the angle of invasion, we average over the first 5 z-slices just below the surface; this entails an average over 2.5 micrometers in the axial direction.

Molecular fracture sensor

The mechano-sensitive spiropyran crosslinker was synthesized by adapting a protocol established in [7]. The molecule is designed to carry two vinyl functional groups, placed on opposite sides of the scissile spiro bond, that incorporate into the PDMS network covalently, thereby allowing the molecule to act as a crosslinker to ensure force transfer from the polymer matrix onto the mechanophore. The mode of action of these fracture reporters is illustrated in S2: In the absence of force the molecule spiropyran is in a non-fluorescent state. Application of mechanical stress leads to rupture of the central reversible-covalent spiro-bond. This mechanical conversion transforms the molecule into merocyanine a colored and fluorescent compound. Fluorescence emission is thus observed in loci where the stress has exceeded the rupture force for the spiropyran and is used as a proxy for detecting mechanical damage in the substrate.

Figure S5.2. Illustration of how mechanical stress can convert non-fluorescent spiropyran (1) to the fluo-rescent merocyanine (2).

Synthesis

Figure S5.3. Illustration of spiropyran synthesis step 1.

Step 1: To a roundbottom flask, 5 mL of trimethylindolenine (31.4 mmol) was added. Then 3.67 mL of 2-iodoethanol (47.1 mmol) was introduced together with 56 mL of anhydrous toluene. The reaction was left under reflux for 20 hours before cooling. The product was collected by vacuum filtration. The resulting light pink solid which was washed with 210 mL of 2% (v/v) EtOH in Et₂O to remove residual 2-iodoethanol and dried under vacuum. Yield = 1.18 gram (11.3%).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 7.97 ppm (m, 1H), 7.85 (m, 1H), 7.64 (m, 2H), 4.61 (m, 2H), 3.88 (m, 2H), 2.83 (s, 3H), 2.50 (s, 3H), 1.56 (s, 6H).

Figure S5.4. Illustration of spiropyran synthesis step 2.

Step 2: To obtain the intermediate product **4**, 5.020 g of 2-hydroxy,3-methoxy,5-nitrobenzaldehyde was dissolved in 94 ml of 48% HBr and left to reflux for 4.5 hours, diluted with 300 mL water and cooled. The reaction mixture was subsequently filtered and the solid product washed with 200 ml water and dried in-vacuo. Yield = 4.02 gram (86.1%).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 11.78 ppm (s, 1H), 10.01 (s, 1H), 8.21 (d, 1H), 8.07 (d, 1H), 5.96 (s, 1H).

Figure S5.5. Illustration of spiropyran synthesis step 3.

Step 3: In a roundbottom flask, 1.035g of **2** (3.12 mmol) and 0.5727g of **4** (3.12 mmol) were dissolved in 25 ml ethanol. To this, 0.874 ml triethylamine (6.24 mmol) was added and the solution was brought to reflux and stirred for 2 hours. After cooling, the solution was filtered and the resulting precipitate washed with cold ethanol. The filtrate was concentrated and filtered to maximize yield; this was repeated three

times. Yield = 0.83 gram (76.7%). No proton NMR was recorded for this intermediate product.

Figure S5.6. Illustration of spiroopyran synthesis step 4.

Step 4: In the last step, 0.6022g of **5** (1.628 mmol) was added to a roundbottom flask along with 0.0215g 4-dimethylaminopyridine (0.1628 mmol). This was dissolved in 8 mL DCM. Under nitrogen flow, 0.64 mL of 4-pentenoic anhydride (3.502 mmol) was added dropwise at a rate of 1 drop per 15 minutes using a syringe. The reaction was left to stir under nitrogen overnight, resulting in a purple solution. This mixture was extracted against 75 ml each of: concentrated $\text{Na}(\text{HCO}_3)_2$, 1M HCl, water (2x) and brine. The organic phase was dried over magnesium sulphate and filtered, after which the filtrate was evaporated to yield product **7**. Yield = 0.62 gram (73%).

^1H NMR (400MHz, DMSO-d_6) δ 7.96 ppm (d, 1H), 7.85 (d, 1H), 7.18 (td, 1H), 7.08 (d, 1H), 6.97 (d, 1H), 6.88 (m, 1H), 6.67 (d, 1H), 5.97 (d, 1H), 5.78 (m, 1H), 5.58 (ddt, 1H), 4.93 (m, 4H), 4.25 (m, 1H), 4.18 (m, 1H), 3.35 (t, 2H), 2.37 (m, 4H), 2.21 (m, 2H), 1.88 (m, 2H), 1.29 (s, 3H), 1.20 (s, 3H).

Product **7** was dissolved in toluene at 75 mg/ml for addition to the PDMS base at a final concentration of 10 mg spiroopyran / 1 gram PDMS. The stock solution in toluene was added to the Sylgard 184 base+crosslinker mixture and homogenized thoroughly. The resulting mixture was spin-coated onto cleaned glass slides at 2000 rpm to obtain layers of approximately 35 μm . Spincoated glass slides were first placed inside a vacuum chamber for 30 min to remove air bubbles after which they were cured at 50°C overnight.

Validation

To confirm that fluorescence detected in the substrate is due to mechanical activation we also synthesized both version of **7** that carries only a single vinyl group. The monovinyl spiroopyran binds only on one side to the PDMS network and is therefore not able to carry a mechanical stress and should not activate when the substrate is damaged mechanically. Indeed, even upon severe damage induction in the substrate, by scratching, no fluorescence is detected (Figure S7A), while similar treatment on the divinyl, and hence mechano-active, reporter reveals a fluorescence pattern in the shape of the damage; here performed by indenting the surface using a W-shaped stamp (Figure S7C). Finally, we verify that this lack of fluorescence signal after mechanical activation of the mono-vinyl reporter is not due to a lack of incorporation by rapidly converting all spiroopyran to meryocanine using a UV light pulse; and as expected, this leads to a large fluorescence signal (Figure S7B). This confirms that while the monovinyl moiety is incorporated it is not mechanically active. Any signal we observe during pathogenic invasion in the divinyl

spiropyran-loaded substrate is thus due to mechanical stress, validating its use as a proxy-reported for mechanical damage in the substrate.

Figure S5.7. Panel A; Monovinyl spiropyran incorporated PDMS slab, cut using a scalpel. Panel B; Same slab as in A, UV pulsed to convert the spiropyran to merocyanine. Panel C; Divinyl spiropyran incorporated PDMS slab, stamped using a "W".

Surface deformation profiling

To quantify the mechanics of surface invasion we develop an approach to map the surface deformation profile with high resolution. To do so, we record three-dimensional time series of fluorescent PDMS elastomer surfaces (see sections 'Imaging Protocol' and 'Substrates' for details) during invasion of *Phytophthora* spp. For each xy -pixel we then extract the intensity profile of the PDMS layer as a function of the position in z ; to suppress spurious noise we average the intensity using nearest-neighbour cross averaging. A sigmoidal decay is observed of the fluorescence intensity across the PDMS-water interface. For each pixel in the xy -plane these intensity profiles are fitted to the sigmoidal function:

$$I(z) = \frac{I_{bulk}}{1 + \exp(-(z - z_0))}$$

in which I_{bulk} sets the plateau intensity in the bulk of the elastomer slab and z_0 is the centroid position of the decay, which defines the local surface height, the quantity of interest.

After reconstruction of the surface height map for the entire three-dimensional image, we perform a tilt correction to correct for small deviations in sample placement from the horizontal axis. We find that most samples are tilted by at most 1-2°. Tilt corrections are done from the outer 10 micrometers of the field of view, by fitting the tilt to a linear polynomial function in both the x and y directions. Finally, the median value of the height map is subtracted from each pixel to bring the substrate normal to $z = 0$, resulting in relative surface height maps. We use a linear approximation to ensure that no splay of the surface is induced by the de-tilting algorithm.

To determine the δz_0 -resolution of our method, we record image stacks of a substrate in the absence of any microbes. This results in flat surface height maps with fluctuations of amplitude δz_0 due to the diffraction-limited images and statistical errors in the fitting procedure. Histograms of δz_0 for this experiment show a Gaussian distribution. We define the resolution as the FWHM of this distribution. Due to the use of the entire z -intensity profile to determine the surface height, we obtain a resolution in z_0 , with sub-pixel accuracy, of 46 nm for the highest resolution imaging settings used (z -step = 0.125 μ m).

Mechanical model

Model & fitting

The pathogen applies a pressure to the substrate by generating pushing forces in a localized region with its tip. To indent and penetrate the substrate, this pushing force must be balanced by a force in the opposite direction brought about by an adhesion site. The total indentation force \mathbf{F}_i applied to the indentation site can be decomposed in a normal force $P_i = F_i \cos \theta$ and a tangential force $Q_i = F_i \sin \theta$, where θ is the angle of indentation. Mechanical equilibrium implies that these forces are balanced by forces in the adhesion site $P_a = -P_i$ and $Q_a = -Q_i$. We treat the elastic substrate as a linear elastic solid, characterized by a shear modulus G and a Poisson ration ν , and assume that both the tip and the adhesion region of the pathogen can be described as indenters with an ellipsoidal shape. This allows us to model the forces generated by the pathogen as a Hertzian stress distribution applied over elliptical regions [6]:

$$\mathbf{p}_i(x, y) = \frac{3\mathbf{F}_i}{2\pi a_i b_i} \left[1 - \left(\frac{x - x_{c,i}}{a_i} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{y - y_{c,i}}{b_i} \right)^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

in the indentation site, i.e. within the region bounded by the ellipse

$$\left(\frac{x - x_{c,i}}{a_i}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{y - y_{c,i}}{b_i}\right)^2 \leq 1$$

where $x_{c,i}$ and $y_{c,i}$ denote the coordinates of the center of the indentation site, and a_i and b_i the length and width of the indentation site, respectively. Similarly, for the adhesion site

$$\mathbf{p}_a(x, y) = -\frac{3\mathbf{F}_i}{2\pi a_a b_a} \left[1 - \left(\frac{x - x_{c,a}}{a_a}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{y - y_{c,a}}{b_a}\right)^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

for

$$\left(\frac{x - x_{c,a}}{a_a}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{y - y_{c,a}}{b_a}\right)^2 \leq 1$$

Here, the x -axis is taken in the direction of the tangential force, corresponding to the axis through the centers of the indentation and adhesion sites, so that $y_{c,i} = y_{c,a} = 0$. The total stress distribution at the surface is $\mathbf{p}(x, y) = \mathbf{p}_i(x, y) + \mathbf{p}_a(x, y)$ and has normal and tangential components, as specified by the angle θ .

Within linear elasticity theory, the three-dimensional displacement \mathbf{u} (with components u_x , u_y , and u_z) at any point in the elastic material due to this applied stress distribution can be found by integration:

$$\mathbf{u}(x, y, z) = \int \int \mathbf{G}(x - x', y - y', z) \mathbf{p}(x', y') dx' dy' \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{G}(x - x', y - y', z)$ is the Green's function that gives the response at position (x, y, z) due to a concentrated force at (x', y', z') . For the normal component of the force p_z , this is given by the Boussinesq relations [6]:

$$G_{xz}(x, y, z) = \frac{p_z}{4\pi G} \left[\frac{xz}{\rho^3} - (1 - 2\nu) \frac{x}{\rho(\rho + z)} \right] \quad (4)$$

$$G_{yz}(x, y, z) = \frac{p_z}{4\pi G} \left[\frac{yz}{\rho^3} - (1 - 2\nu) \frac{y}{\rho(\rho + z)} \right] \quad (5)$$

$$G_{zz}(x, y, z) = \frac{p_z}{4\pi G} \left[\frac{z^2}{\rho^3} + \frac{2(1 - \nu)}{\rho} \right] \quad (6)$$

with $\rho = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}$. For the tangential component q_x (in the x -direction) this is given by the Cerruti relations [6]:

$$G_{xx}(x, y, z) = \frac{q_x}{4\pi G} \left[\frac{1}{\rho} + \frac{x^2}{\rho^3} + (1 - 2\nu) \frac{1}{\rho + z} - \frac{x^2}{\rho(\rho + z)^2} \right] \quad (7)$$

$$G_{yx}(x, y, z) = \frac{q_x}{4\pi G} \left[\frac{yz}{\rho^3} - (1 - 2\nu) \frac{xy}{\rho(\rho + z)^2} \right] \quad (8)$$

$$G_{zx}(x, y, z) = \frac{q_x}{4\pi G} \left[\frac{xz}{\rho^3} + (1 - 2\nu) \frac{x}{\rho(\rho + z)} \right] \quad (9)$$

Using equations 1–9, we obtain the full displacement profile in the solid by numerical integration for given \mathbf{F}_i , $x_{c,i}$, $x_{c,a}$, a_i , b_i , a_a and b_a . The displacement at the surface follows by setting $z = 0$ in equations 4-9.

The stress tensor at position (x, y, z) is obtained using Hooke's law:

$$\sigma_{ij} = \lambda \delta_{ij} u_{k,k} + \mu (u_{i,j} + u_{j,i}) \quad (10)$$

where $\lambda = 2G\nu/(1 - 2\nu)$ and $\mu = G$ are the Lamé coefficients, δ_{ij} is Kronecker's delta function and where the spatial derivatives $u_{i,j}$ are obtained from the displacement profile $u_i(x, y, z)$ by numerical differentiation. The principal stresses, finally, are obtained as the eigenvalues of the stress tensor. In our calculations, we have taken a Poisson ratio $\nu = 0.45$ and a Young's modulus $E = 0.58$ MPa, as measured (see section 'Substrates') corresponding to a shear modulus $G = E/2(1 + \nu) = 0.23$ MPa. The angle of invasion was fixed at the angle determined experimentally (see section 'Invasion angle measurements') at $\theta = 49^\circ$.

The mechanical model was fitted to the experimental data using only the geometrical parameters and the total indentation force as the adjustable parameters. Since the set of equations is highly non-linear we adopted a simulated-annealing approach to fit model to experimental profiles. In the fitting procedure, a Monte Carlo algorithm creates a random mutation to the fit parameters and determines the Sum-of-Squares error between fit and data. If the SoS is reduced with respect to the previous iteration, the change is accepted. If the SoS increases, it is accepted with a 'Boltzmann' probability; this step is ensured to enable the escape from local fitting minima. For each curve, the routine is repeated for 10000 iterations to achieve an optimal fit result. Convergence of the model to the experimental data is usually observed within 1000-2000 steps.

Figure S5.8. Aggregated data for the geometrical features of indentation (a_1 and b_1) and adhesion sites (a_2 and b_2) and connection distance d from fitting of time-series of surface deformation profiles for 3 *P. infestans* - 14:3 GFP invaders.

Figure S5.9. Aggregated data for the geometrical features of indentation (a_1 and b_1) and adhesion sites (a_2 and b_2) and connection distance d from fitting of time-series of surface deformation profiles for 3 *P. palmivora* - wt invaders.

Figure S5.10. Calculated stress fields inside the substrate upon naifu-indentation. These data are the result of first fitting our model to experimental surface deformation profiles to extract the geometrical parameters and the applied force, which together with the independently measured substrate modulus, is used to predict stress fields in all primary components of the stress tensor (sample: *P. infestans-wt* at the moment just prior to surface fracture). This data is an accompaniment to main text Figure 3c. Substrate interface is located at $z = 0$, indentation site at $(x = 0, z = 0)$.

Inhibiting polarized growth by LatB

To verify the role of the actin cytoskeleton in the mechanical invasion of *Phytophthora* spp. we perform experiments in the presence of the actin depolymerizing drug Latrunculin B (LatB). Previous work has indicated that LatB doses of >250 nM suppresses the formation of actin cables in *P. infestans*, while lower doses slow down polarised growth substantially [8,9]. Here we study the force generation capacity

of *P. infestans* - wt in the presence of 100 nM, 500 nM and 1 μ M Latrunculin B, in the presence of 1% DMSO to solubilize the drug. As controls, we also study the invasion of the same species in pure medium (sterilized tap water) and in medium with 1% DMSO without LatB. In all experiments, to 500 μ L of diluted cyst suspension we add the desired amount of LatB from a stock solution in DMSO, ensuring a final DMSO concentration with respect to medium of 1%. The treated cyst suspension is used to inoculate fluorescent PDMS elastomer substrates ($E = 0.58$ MPa), which are left for 2h before commencing the imaging (2 hours post-inoculation, 2hpi), as described above.

Inhibiting substrate adhesion

Force balance dictates that the downward pressure applied by the pathogen onto its host to achieve entry must be balanced by an upward force of equal magnitude. Balance can only be accomplished by adhesion of the germ tube onto the substrate, also revealed by our surface deformation mapping. Suppression of adhesion logically should prevent the application of indentation pressure and thus stop mechanical host entry. To test this hypothesis, we have coated our PDMS surfaces with a pLL-g-PEG [10] polymer that results in a strongly hydrated and hydrophilic surface, which is known to effectively suppress adhesion of biomolecules and microbes. The coating follows established procedures for PDMS [10]; first we expose the PDMS substrates to oxygen/nitrogen plasma to activate the PDMS and generate anionic binding groups. Then, the activated slides are coated with the pLL-g-PEG polymers by spincoating 150 μ L of a 0.1 mg/ml solution of pLL-g-PEG in HEPES buffer (pH=7.4) onto the substrate. This resulted in a obvious change in the contact angle of water droplets, turning the hydrophobic PDMS very hydrophilic. These substrates were inoculated as described above and imaging performed 2hpi.

Inhibiting turgor generation

The proposed main force generation method requires a high turgor pressure, in line with observations of filamentous plant pathogens [11, 12]. A common method to assess internal turgor pressure of invasive phytopathogens is the usage of PEG [11] to decrease the pressure differential between cell and surroundings. According to the Van t Hoff law, osmotic pressure decreases when the concentration of osmolytes between inside and outside the cells becomes more equal. We used a 400 g/l PEG-2000 stock solution (.2M) and MQ water to dilute cyst suspensions to assess the effect of high surrounding turgor on the invasion process. To clarify, we added the osmolytes only after sporulation and encystment steps to ensure that the difference between control and treated cells is only present at the invasion stage, not during sporulation itself. After addition of the high turgor pressures we deposited the cysts on the PDMS surfaces for 2 hours before commencing the imaging, as described above. All measurements were done under standard PDMS modulus (.58 MPa).

Code availability

All codes used in this study are available on GitHub, when following this [link](https://github.com/jorissprakel/Phytophthora_invasion). If the linking does not work: https://github.com/jorissprakel/Phytophthora_invasion.

Additional data

Figure S5.11. Examples of non-bandpass filtered images of spiropyran activation *P. infestans* - *14-3eGFP* showing distinct mechanically-gated fluorophore activation at the apex of the hyphal tip. Scale bars represent 5 micrometers.

Table S3. Experimental details

Experiment	Figure	Sample numbers
In-planta invasion angle	Fig.1a	* (<i>P. infestans</i> - 14/3): N = 15 (from 5 independent experiments)
Invasion angles	Fig.1d-i	* 0.56 MPa (<i>P. infestans</i> - 14/3): N = 200 (from 8 independent experiments) * 1.49 MPa (<i>P. infestans</i> - 14/3): N = 303 (from 3 independent experiments) * 1.84 MPa (<i>P. infestans</i> - 14/3): N = 126 (from 2 independent experiments) * 0.56 MPa (<i>P. infestans</i> - wt): N = 115 (from 2 independent experiments) * 0.56 MPa (<i>P. palmivora</i> - wt): N = 94 (from 2 independent experiments) * 0.56 MPa (<i>P. capsici</i> - wt): N = 68 (from 3 independent experiments)
Fracture sensor	Fig.2b and Extended Data Figure 1	* 0.10 MPa <i>P. infestans</i> - 14/3: N = 19 (from 3 independent experiments)
Surface deformation maps	Fig.2f and Extended Data Figure 2 Fig.2g and Extended Data Figure 3 Extended Data Figure 4 Extended Data Figure 5	* 0.56 MPa (<i>P. infestans</i> - 14/3 eGFP): N = 6 (from 3 independent experiments) * 0.56 MPa (<i>P. palmivora</i> - wt): N = 7 (from 3 independent experiments) * 0.56 MPa (<i>P. infestans</i> - wt): N = 6 (from 4 independent experiments) * 0.56 MPa (<i>P. capsici</i> - wt): N = 8 (from 4 independent experiments)
Fitting to mechanical model	Fig.3d and Extended Data Fig.6 Fig.3e	* 0.56 MPa (<i>P. infestans</i> - 14/3): N = 3 (from 3 independent experiments) * 0.56 MPa (<i>P. palmivora</i> - wt): N = 2 (from 2 independent experiments)
Actin depolymerization with LatB	Fig.4	0.56 MPa <i>P. infestans</i> - wt: * control: N=111 (10 FoVs, 2 independent expt) * +1% DMSO: N=106 (8 FoVs, 2 independent expts) * +1% DMSO + 100 nM LatB: N=368 (8 FoVs, 2 independent expt) * +1% DMSO + 500 nM LatB: N=142 (9 FoVs, 2 independent expt) * +1% DMSO + 1 μ M LatB: N=153 (8 FoVs, 2 independent expts)
Adhesion suppression with PEG-g-PLL	Fig.4	0.56 MPa <i>P. infestans</i> - wt: * +PEG-g-PLL treated PDMS: N=74 (16 FOVs, 2 independent expts)
Osmotic treatment (2h post-inocc.)	Fig.4	0.56 MPa <i>P. infestans</i> - wt: * +5.0 bar: N=105 (4 FOVs, 2 independent expts) * +13.2 bar: N=45 (4 FOVs, 2 independent expt) * +27.8 bar: N=20 (4 FOVs, 2 independent expt)
Leaf infection (7d post-inocc.)	Extended Data Figure 7	<i>P. infestans</i> - wt on <i>Nb-sobir1</i> leaves: * positive control LatB (zoospores + no treatment): N=48 leaves (4 independent expts) * negative control (no zoospores + no treatment): N=20 leaves (1 independent expt) * 1% DMSO: N=8 leaves (1 independent expt) * 0.1mM LatB + 1% DMSO: N=20 leaves (3 independent expts) * 1mM LatB + 1% DMSO: N=48 leaves (4 independent expts) * positive control PEGMA (zoospores + no coating): N=16 leaves (2 independent expts) * PEGMA treatment: N=16 leaves (2 independent expts)

References used in supplementary information

- [1] Elysa J. R. Overdijk et al. Interaction between the moss *Physcomitrella patens* and *Phytophthora* : a novel pathosystem for live-cell imaging of subcellular defence. *Journal Of Microscopy* Volume 263, Issue 2 (2016)
- [2] C P Woloshuk, J S Meulenhoff, M Sela-Buurlage, P J van den Elzen & B J Cornelissen. Pathogen-induced proteins with inhibitory activity toward *Phytophthora infestans*. *The Plant Cell* Vol. 3, Issue 6, June (1991)
- [3] G. Mchau & M. Coffey. Isozyme diversity in *Phytophthora palmivora*: evidence for a southeast Asian centre of origin. *Mycological Research*, (1994), 1035-1043, 98(9)
- [4] J. Miao, M. Cai, X. Dong, L. Liu, D. Lin, C. Zhang, Z. Pang & X. Liu. Resistance Assessment for Oxathiapiprolin in *Phytophthora capsici* and the Detection of a Point Mutation (G769W) in PcORP1 that Confers Resistance. *Front. Microbiol.* 7:615 (2016)
- [5] J. N. M. Boots, R. Fokkink, J. van der Gucht & T. E. Kodger. Development of a multi-position indentation setup: Mapping soft and patternable heterogeneously crosslinked polymer networks. *Review of Scientific Instruments* 90, 015108 (2019)
- [6] Johnson, K. L. *Contact Mechanics*. (1985).
- [7] Davis, D.A. et al. Force-induced activation of covalent bonds in mechanoresponsive polymeric materials. *Nature* 459, 68-72 (2009).
- [8] Meijer HJG et al. Actin dynamics in *Phytophthora infestans*; rapidly reorganizing cables and immobile, long-lived plaques. *Cell Microbiol* 16(6):948–961 (2014)
- [9] Tijs Ketelaar et al. Effects of latrunculin B on the actin cytoskeleton and hyphal growth in *Phytophthora infestans* *Fungal Genetics and Biology*, (2012), 1014-1022, 49(12)
- [10] Lee S. and Vörös J. An Aqueous-Based Surface Modification of Poly(dimethylsiloxane) with Poly(ethylene glycol) to Prevent Biofouling. *Langmuir*, 21, 25, 11957–11962 (2005)
- [11] Howard, R. J. et al. Penetration of hard substrates by a fungus employing enormous turgor pressures. *PNAS*, 11281-11284, 88(24) (1991)
- [12] Johns, Scott et al. Pulses in turgor pressure and water potential: Resolving the mechanics of hyphal growth. *Microbiological Research*, 225-231, 154(3) (1999)